

SEXUAL ORIENTATION AND ACCEPTANCE TO HETERONORMATIVE BELIEFS TOWARD STUDENT NURSES' CLINICAL PERFORMANCE

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Sexual Orientation and Acceptance to Heteronormative Beliefs toward Student Nurses' Clinical Performance

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the relationship between the level of acceptance of heteronormative beliefs to the clinical performance of 4th-year BSN students of Riverside College, Inc. Different variables were examined, such as sex, sexual orientation, and religion. The descriptive-correlational research design was utilized using a quantitative method conducted with 97 4th-year BSN students using Habarth's Heteronormative Attitudes and Beliefs Scale (HABS). This study revealed that there is no significant correlation using Pearson Correlation between the level of acceptance of heteronormative beliefs when correlated to the clinical performance of 4th-year BSN students. Their level of acceptance of heteronormative beliefs, when grouped according to the aforementioned variables, posited a high acceptance level. As to their clinical performance, 4th-year BSN students have very good clinical performance regardless of sex, sexual orientation, and religion, and it does not affect the quality of care that they provide among patients with diverse beliefs and sexual identities. The researcher proposed that a gender equality program be implemented to enhance gender inclusion among nursing students and clinical instructors while also increasing the quality of nursing practice and education in both academic and clinical settings.

Keywords: *clinical performance, heteronormative beliefs, nursing students*

Introduction

Heteronormative beliefs have become one of the most active areas of public opinion in shaping our society's norms. These are based on the notion that males and females have separate qualities and duties, as well as fixed behavioral expectations for males and females. According to Habarth (2015, as referenced by Duncan, Aguilar, Jensen, & Magnusson, 2019), acceptance of heteronormative attitudes is linked to negative sentiments toward gender nonconformity. Living as a gender non-conforming person has been linked to a higher risk of long-term social stresses, such as stigmatization, as well as poorer health-related quality of life outcomes (Gordon et al., 2017).

The individuals who are traditionally gender conforming can also be badly affected by heteronormative beliefs. The persons who dress and conduct according to feminine norms have lower self-esteem than those who dress and behave according to masculine norms (Spivey, 2018). Males who are conflicted about violating the masculine gender role by expressing emotion or care toward other men are less likely to seek professional psychological help for mental illness and have more unfavorable attitudes about seeking help in general (Huang, 2018). Men have also been observed to face backlash while participating in female-dominated communal responsibilities, according to Croft et al. (2015, as cited by Ellemer, 2018). While these examples are not definitive, and there are benefits to following traditional gender roles, it is evident that heteronormative gender roles impact everyone.

On the other hand, Chan (2002, as referenced by Arkan, Ordin, & Yilmaz, 2018) said that the clinical education environment is a social milieu in which individuals have varying expectations and requirements, and where control over the factors that affect learning is limited. Because they are in a stage of life marked by rapid growth of personal beliefs and identity, college students are an important demographic for studying gender norms (Potts, 2017). They also represent a more diversified collection of students than the graduate education subcategory. Because discrimination against LGBT students, many of whom are not gender conforming, is frequent on college campuses, surveying an undergraduate sample is especially significant for this study (Seelman et al., 2017). Furthermore, Rahmani et al. (2011, as quoted by Arkan, Ordin, & Yilmaz, 2018) claimed that these characteristics of the clinical environment make it difficult to provide suitable learning circumstances for students and cause problems in the learning process.

Recognizing the importance of one's sexual orientation, the perspectives on heteronormative beliefs in society, and personal identity crisis, the researcher is motivated to look into the relationship between sexual orientation, heteronormative beliefs and nursing students' clinical performance. Furthermore, the researcher believes that it is critical to provide information and understanding regarding gender inclusion, as well as develop safe spaces for both heterosexuals and sexual minorities to both instructors and students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of acceptance of heteronormative beliefs and its relationship with the clinical performance rating of fourth-year BSN students with varied gender identities enrolled in a private institution in Bacolod City for the School Year 2021-2022. Moreover, the salient findings of this study served as a basis in constructing a gender equality program for students, nursing educators, academic and clinical institutions. Specifically, the researcher answered the following research questions:

1. What is the level of acceptance of 4th year BSN students towards the heteronormative beliefs as a whole and when grouped according to:
 - 1.1. sex,

- 1.2. sexual orientation, and
- 1.3. religion?
2. What is the clinical performance rating of 4th year BSN students as a whole and when grouped according to:
 - 2.1. sex,
 - 2.2. sexual orientation, and
 - 2.3. religion?
3. Is there a significant difference in the level of acceptance of 4th year BSN students towards the heteronormative beliefs as whole and when grouped according to:
 - 3.1. sex,
 - 3.2. sexual orientation, and
 - 3.3. religion?
4. Is there a significant difference in the clinical performance rating of 4th year BSN students as a whole and when grouped according to:
 - 4.1. sex,
 - 4.2. sexual orientation, and
 - 4.3. religion?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of acceptance towards heteronormative beliefs and clinical performance rating of 4th year BSN students?
6. What gender equality program may be developed to provide a safe space conducive for learning based on the level of acceptance towards heteronormative beliefs and clinical performance rating of 4th year BSN students?

Methodology

Research Design

This study aims to determine the level of acceptance of heteronormative beliefs and its relationship with the clinical performance rating of fourth year BSN students enrolled in a private institution in Bacolod City for School Year 2021-2022. In this sense, the researcher utilizes Descriptive Research Design as the primary blueprint on how to address the research questions. As a type of research design, Descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation or phenomenon (Mccombes, 2019). Moreover, descriptive method uses a wide variety of quantitative and qualitative methods to investigate one or more variables. Through survey, the researcher gathers and identifies sufficient and exact information.

Furthermore, this study uses Comparative Research Design to determine whether a significant difference exists in the level of acceptance towards the heteronormative beliefs and in the clinical performance of 4th year BSN students according to sex, sexual orientation, and religion. This study also used Documentary Analysis to retrieve the RLE grades of fourth-year BSN students from 1st and 2nd semester of Academic Year 2019-2020 which will be the basis of their clinical performance rating. According to Ahmed (2010, as cited by Bailey, 1994), documentary research method refers to the analysis of documents that contains information about the phenomenon the researcher wish to study. On the other hand, Correlational Research Design was utilized to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the level of acceptance towards heteronormative beliefs and clinical performance rating of the respondents. Finally, the researcher used survey method and testing using a standardized questionnaire to identify the sexual orientation and level of acceptance towards the heteronormative beliefs of the respondents, respectively.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the fourth-year nursing students of Riverside College, Inc. who are enrolled in the first semester of academic year 2021-2022 and are included in both old and new curriculums.

The researcher surveyed 97 fourth-year BSN students as the participants of this study using the homogenous sampling, a type of purposive sampling method, which focuses on candidates who share similar traits or specific characteristics (Etikan, Musa, & Alkassim, 2016).

Profile of the participants

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of participants in terms of sex, sexual orientation and religion. There were 82 (84%) female and only 15 (16%) males out of 97 total number of participants. In terms of sexual orientation, there were 76 (78%) heterosexual which comprised the most number compare to those who belong to the 21 (22%) sexual minorities; which includes 2 (2%) asexuals, 13 (14%) bisexuals, 4 (4%) gays/lesbians, 1 (1%) pansexual and 1 (1%) participant that has an unlisted sexual orientation. As to the participants' religion, there were 70 (72%) who belong to the Roman Catholic, 21 (22%) Christian (including Protestant and all other Christian Denominations), 1 (1%) Muslim, 1 (1%) Unaffiliated to any religion and 4 (%) who belongs to any other religion.

Table 1. *Distribution of Study Participants*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Sex		
Male	15	16
Female	82	84
Sexual Orientation		
Asexual	2	2
Bisexual	13	14
Gay/Lesbian	4	4
Heterosexual/Straight	76	78
Pansexual	1	1
Unlisted	1	1
Religion		
Roman Catholic	70	72
Christian	21	22
Muslim	1	1
Unaffiliated	1	1
Other religions	4	4
As a whole	97	100

Instruments

The research instrument used in this study was the standardized questionnaire Heteronormative Attitudes and Beliefs Scale (HABS) by Dr. Janice Habarth in 2015. The instrument consisted of 2 parts in which the first part aimed to gather the personal data of the participants which are: sex, sexual orientation and religion. The second part of the questionnaire consisted of the questions from Heteronormative Attitudes and Beliefs Scale (HABS) which was utilized to measure the level of acceptance to heteronormative beliefs. It contains sixteen (16) statements under heteronormative attitudes and beliefs. The HABS could be divided into two subscales: the Essential Sex and Gender subscale that addresses beliefs about gender, and the Normative Behavior subscale which addresses sex role expectations within romantic relationships. Subscale scores were created by averaging relevant items (Duncan, Aguilar, Jensen, & Magnusson, 2019). Using the questionnaire with the 7-point Likert rating scale which includes (7) Strongly Agree, (6) Agree, (5) Somewhat Agree, (4) Neutral, (3) Somewhat Disagree, (2) Disagree, and (1) Strongly Disagree; the researcher will be able to gather concise and precise information that will be used to answer the research questions.

Validity and Reliability

Reliability (Cronbach's α) for the HABS is reported as .92 for Essential Sex and Gender and .78 for Normative Behaviour Scale. Dr. Habarth (2015) reported that the instrument acquired adequate contemporaneous validity with these closely related constructs on RWA (Right Wing Attitudes) and ATLG (Attitudes Toward Lesbians and Gays) during the development of HABS.

Dr. Habarth used a Direct Oblimin-rotated factor analysis of the 38 initial items in the development of HABS in 2015, and discovered two factors with eigenvalues of 10.3 and 6.6 (the scree plot suggested a two-factor solution). In the following analyses, items with absolute value factor loadings of at least 0.5 on one factor and less than 0.3 on the other were kept. This resulted in a 16-item heteronormativity scale consisting of two eight-item measures with balanced negative/positive wording ($r = 0.42$, $p < 0.01$). The scales Essential Sex and Gender ($\alpha = 0.92$) and Normative Behaviour ($\alpha = 0.78$), respectively, reflect the two theorized components of heteronormativity.

Procedure

Before commencing the data gathering, the researcher obtained the Dean of the College of Nursing's approval for the study's conduct. Then, a letter of authorization to perform the study was given to the Center for Research and Publication.

The researcher delivered the test to the participants with the approval of their level adviser using the HABS questionnaire via Microsoft Forms in the LMS platform Microsoft Teams. To avoid misunderstandings, the researcher instructed the participants on how to complete the test and clarified specific problems. Following these preliminaries, the participants were given 10 to 20 minutes to complete the questionnaire. When the students have finished, the questionnaires were promptly retrieved, and the data were tallied, evaluated, and interpreted by the researcher in order to solve the problem with responses and reach a correct conclusion.

Data Analysis

The following were the statistical tools to be utilized in interpreting the results:

For research question number 1, which aims to determine the level of acceptance of 4th year BSN students towards the heteronormative beliefs as a whole and when grouped according to sex, sexual orientation and religion, mean and standard deviation were utilized.

For research question number 2, which focuses on the clinical performance rating of 4th year BSN students as a whole and when grouped according to sex, sexual orientation and religion, mean and standard deviation were used.

For research question number 3, to determine the level of heteronormative acceptance and beliefs, as well as the clinical performance of the 4th year BSN students when they were grouped according to the study variables, mean was computed.

To ascertain whether there was a significant difference in the heteronormative acceptance and beliefs and in the clinical performance of the BSN 4 students in research question number 4, t-Test for independent means was used for the variable sex and One-Way ANOVA for the variables sexual orientation and religion.

To find out if there was a significant relationship between the level of heteronormative acceptance and beliefs and clinical performance of 4th year BSN students, Pearson Correlation Coefficient was computed.

All tests for significance were set at 95% level of confidence.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher had sought the respondents' informed consent while maintaining the respondents' anonymity and the data's confidentiality. Before getting informed consent from the respondents, the researcher explained the study's rationale and major intention, as well as how the findings will not influence their academic standing. In addition, each respondent received an informed consent document in addition to the questionnaire.

Meanwhile, in order to protect the respondents' anonymity, the respondents' questionnaires were identified by a code rather than their names. The researcher focused on data protection and storage during the data collection and analysis phase to ensure the safekeeping of electronic and hardcopy connected to the study. To comply with ethical guidelines, these data were disposed of a week after the retention period has expired. The survey questionnaires, which were physical sources of research data, were removed from Microsoft Forms with no way of retrieving them.

Results and Discussion

This section includes the interpretation of data gathered, presented, and aligned to the investigation's problem, as well as data analysis using appropriate statistical methods. To aid in the discussion of the results, tabular and graphical presentations are also provided.

Table 2. Level of Heteronormative Acceptance and Beliefs of BSN 4 Students

Variable	M	Level of Acceptance
Sex		
Male	4.73	High
Female	4.74	High
Sexual Orientation		
Asexual	5.03	Rather high
Bisexual	4.92	High
Gay/Lesbian	4.14	Moderate
Heterosexual/Straight	4.73	High
Pansexual	5.56	Rather high
Unlisted	4.31	Moderate
Religion		
Roman Catholic	4.78	High
Christian	4.60	High
Muslim	5.56	Rather high
Unaffiliated	4.50	High
Other religions	4.63	High
As a whole	4.74	High

Table 2 shows the level of acceptance of 4th year BSN students towards the heteronormative beliefs as a whole and when grouped according to sex, sexual orientation and religion. The results revealed that both male ($M=4.73$) and female ($M=4.74$) posited a high level of acceptance. This implies that regardless of sex, student nurses have a high level of acceptance to heteronormative beliefs.

According to Habarth (2015), the acceptance of heteronormative ideas may be linked to unfavorable feelings about gender nonconformity. Because gender nonconforming individuals may suffer physical and social suffering as a result of this bias, the potential of a link is worth considering. According to evidence, heteronormative bias and heterosexism are spread through cultural institutions, resulting in widespread prejudice against sexual diversity (Duncan, Aguilar, Jensen, & Magnusson, 2019). Parents' behavior models early beliefs about gender roles and expectations of conformance to some extent (Halpern and Perry- Jenkins, 2016).

When grouped according to sexual orientation, heterosexuals ($M=4.73$) have high level of acceptance and sexual minorities have varying level of acceptance. Asexual ($M=5.03$) and pansexual ($M=5.56$) individuals were found to have a rather high level of acceptance to heteronormative beliefs compared with those who considered themselves as bisexuals ($M=4.92$) that have high level of acceptance; and gays/lesbians ($M=4.14$) and persons with unlisted sexual orientation ($M=4.31$) that have moderate level of acceptance. According to Duncan, Aguilar, Jensen, & Magnusson (2019), negative attitudes toward gender non-conforming behavior have been suggested to stem from a perception of gender non-conforming behavior as a threat to society's traditional sex role structure, implying that higher personal gender conformity is likely to be associated with a negative view of non-conformity.

On the other hand, Croft et al. (2015) implied that individuals who are traditionally gender conforming may also be badly affected by heteronormative ideas. Individuals who dress and conduct according to feminine norms have lower self-esteem than those who dress and behave according to masculine norms. Males who are conflicted about violating the masculine gender role by exhibiting emotion or care toward other men are less likely to seek professional psychological help for mental illness and have a negative attitude regarding receiving help in general. When men take on female-dominated community roles, they have been proven to face blowback. While these examples are not exhaustive, and there are benefits to following traditional gender roles, it is evident that heteronormative gender roles harm everyone.

When grouped according to religion, Muslim ($M=5.56$) sect have a rather high level of acceptance to heteronormative beliefs. Moreover, the results showed that those who are Roman Catholics ($M=4.78$), Christians ($M=4.60$), those who are unaffiliated with any religion ($M=4.50$) and those who are under any other religions ($M=4.63$) have high level of acceptance to heteronormative beliefs. On a study conducted by Schuck and Liddle (2001, as quoted by Hibma, 2018), The participants agreed that religious teachings about homosexuality were the most common source of conflict. Some of the participants claimed they were told they needed to pray about their homosexuality in order to become straight. Others claimed that they had been taught that having intercourse with people of the same gender is bad. The struggle between their sexuality and their faith has cognitive and emotional effects for the participants. Some participants stated that the teaching that God rejected gay people and sentenced them to hell caused them distress. The Participants felt guilty and ashamed because of their sexual orientation. Several of the participants suffered from severe despair, self-loathing, or suicide ideation. Because of their sexual orientation, several people felt ostracized from their religion communities. Some people were afraid that if they told their faith leaders about their sexuality, they would be rejected.

Table 3. *Clinical Performance of BSN 4 Students*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>Description</i>
Sex		
Male	1.41	Very good
Female	1.41	Very good
Sexual Orientation		
Asexual	1.49	Very good
Bisexual	1.36	Very good
Gay/Lesbian	1.47	Very good
Heterosexual/Straight	1.41	Very good
Pansexual	2.00	Good
Unlisted	1.75	Good
Religion		
Roman Catholic	1.39	Very good
Christian	1.46	Very good
Muslim	2.00	Good
Unaffiliated	1.34	Very good
Other religions	1.35	Very good
As a whole	1.41	Very good

Table 3 shows the clinical performance rating of 4th year BSN students as a whole and when grouped according to sex, sexual orientation and religion. The results revealed that both male ($M=1.41$) and female ($M=1.41$) respondents have a very good clinical performance rating. Best practices in nursing, according to Driever (2002), reflect an organization's decision to use evidence-based principles and expertise in patient care, illness management, and related interventions.

When grouped according to sexual orientation, asexuals ($M=1.49$), gays/lesbians ($M=1.47$), heterosexuals ($M=1.41$), and bisexuals ($M=1.36$) were found to have very good clinical performance ratings, while persons with unlisted sexual orientation ($M=2.00$) and pansexuals ($M=2.00$) have good clinical performance ratings. According to American Nurses Association (2015), nurses must treat everyone with respect and compassion, regardless of their sexual orientation, gender identity, or gender expression. When a nurse shows bias or prejudice, it puts the nurse-patient relationship at jeopardy. Nurses must examine their own biases and preconceptions in

order to preserve trust and offer culturally appropriate treatment (Stokes, 2019). It is insufficient to take the stance of "treating all patients equally." According to the American Nurses Association, nurses must aggressively campaign for LGBTQ patients' equality. In addition to delivering culturally appropriate treatment, nurses must advocate for and support equality for the LGBTQ population, according to the Code of Ethics (Stokes, 2019).

When grouped according to religion, those who are unaffiliated with any religion ($M=1.34$) have a very good clinical performance rating, followed by those who are under any other religions ($M=1.35$), Roman Catholics ($M=1.39$) and Christians ($M=1.46$). Moreover, Muslims ($M=2.00$) were found to have a good clinical performance rating. According to Molzahn and Shields (2008, as quoted by Pullen, Mcguire, Farmer, and Dodd, 2015), spiritual needs of service users are occasionally neglected due to healthcare personnel's difficulty in catering to these needs, despite the fact that many people would like to have them addressed. 'Openness to learning about individuals' spiritual views and listening to their nursing needs in a holistic way will enhance nursing care,' Molzahn and Shields added. According to Breggin (1997, as referenced by Pullen, Mcguire, Farmer, & Dodd, 2015), a therapeutic atmosphere of a healing presence is generated for good psycho-spiritual care by expressing an attitude of loving compassion. Several theorists, including Roy, Neuman, and Watkins, include spirituality as a core element and express the belief that competent nursing practice allows for clients' spiritual needs to be met, according to Molzahn and Shields' (2008, as cited by Pullen, Mcguire, Farmer, & Dodd, 2015).

On the other hand, religion, according to Hall (2021), can influence sentiments toward LGBTQ people. According to a 2014 poll of nurse administrators, there is a statistically significant link between religion and anti-LGBTQ sentiments. About a quarter of the people polled said they were highly religious (Klotzbaugh & Spencer, 2014). The facilitators of the study were able to link this to a higher rate of bigotry against LGBTQ people (Klotzbaugh & Spencer, 2014). Nurse administrators are leaders who have the authority to decide on staff training and continuous education. When the administration hinders personnel from receiving proper training, it creates a barrier to providing quality care to LGBTQ patients (Eliason & Chinn, 2018).

Table 4. Significant Difference in the Level of Acceptance to Heteronormative Beliefs of BSN 4 Students

Variable	df	Test Statistic	p	Interpretation
Sex	95	-0.07 ^a	0.944	No significance
Sexual Orientation	5/91	1.49 ^b	0.199	No significance
Religion	4/92	0.84 ^b	0.502	No significance

a - t-Test; b - ANOVA

Table 4 shows the significant difference in the level of acceptance of 4th year BSN students towards the heteronormative beliefs as whole and when grouped according to variables sex ($p=0.944$), sexual orientation ($p=0.199$) and religion ($p=0.502$) where the analysis was at 95% level of confidence. There is no significant difference on the aforementioned variables as shown by the p-values which are above 0.05 level of significance. These findings indicate that regardless of sex, sexual orientation and religion, these heteronormative beliefs are still accepted by the 4th year BSN students. Therefore, the researcher "fail to reject" the null hypothesis.

In relation to the stated results, according to Cottingham (2015), nursing frequently demands nurses to engage in intimate activities, while heteronormativity restricts behaviors, feelings, and relationships in a variety of social settings. Even heterosexual men may employ heteronormative symbols of conformity to battle being misunderstood as gay in the setting of care work, while gay men nurses may use these methods to remain closeted at giving. As a result, it's likely that male caregivers will have to overcome heteronormative preconceptions as well as the emotional demands of the job. Such labor can be done by both heterosexual and non-heterosexual men. In addition, Giuffre and Williams (2000, as cited by Cottingham, 2015), explained that sexual stereotypes and preconceptions are especially salient when the intimate touch of other bodies is involved, as it is in the case of catheterization. Men's touch is often connected with aggressive hypersexuality, whereas women's touch is typically associated with comfort. Medical students gain the skills needed to desexualize physical touch and provide "clinical" care for patients informally, but this type of instruction is typically missing from men's formal nursing education. Men's training typically focuses on what not to do, which makes them more scared of patient claims of inappropriate behavior. This dread that is part of the emotional portion of heteronormative labor, originates from heteronormative preconceptions made by coworkers and superiors that men are incapable of touching female patients in nonsexual ways. Men who work in the care industry must balance the demands of the job with the fact that their physical care methods are "socially ambiguous and unstable," putting them in the position of being questionable practitioners (Underman, 2011).

Table 5. Significant Difference in the Clinical Performance of BSN 4 Students

Variable	df	Test Statistic	p	Interpretation
Sex	95	-0.93 ^a	0.926	No significance
Sexual Orientation	5/91	2.12 ^b	0.070	No significance
Religion	4/92	2.20 ^b	0.075	No significance

a - t-Test; b - ANOVA

Table 5 shows the significant difference in the clinical performance of 4th year BSN students as a whole and when grouped according to sex ($p=0.926$), sexual orientation ($p=0.070$), and religion ($p=0.075$) where the analysis was at 95% level of confidence. There is no

significant difference on the aforementioned variables as shown by the p-values which are above 0.05 level of significance. These findings indicate that regardless of sex, sexual orientation and religion, the clinical performance of 4th year BSN students remains unchanged. Therefore, the researcher “fail to reject” the null hypothesis.

In line with the results presented, the nurses must treat everyone with respect and compassion, regardless of their sexual orientation, gender identity, or gender expression, according to the Code of Ethics for Nurses (American Nurses Association, 2015). When a nurse shows bias or prejudice, it puts the nurse-patient relationship at jeopardy. Nurses must examine their own biases and preconceptions in order to preserve trust and offer culturally appropriate treatment (Stokes, 2019). It is insufficient to take the stance of "treating all patients equally." According to the American Nurses Association, nurses must aggressively campaign for patients' equality. In addition to delivering culturally appropriate treatment, nurses must also advocate for and support equality for the LGBTQ population, according to the Code of Ethics (Stokes, 2019).

The nurses have an ethical and legal responsibility to provide culturally congruent care and apply best practices linked to the LGBTQ community, according to Drieiver (2002, as referenced by Hall, 2021). Variation in care is reduced, and results are improved, when best practices are implemented. The Joint Commission and the American Nurses Association both encourage healthcare workers to follow best practices and advocate for LGBTQ equality. Nurses are encouraged to take the lead in changing current healthcare trends and reducing inequities among LGBTQ people (Stokes, 2019).

Table 6. *Significant Relationship Between the Level of Acceptance to Heteronormative Beliefs and Clinical Performance of BSN 4 Students*

Correlation		Significance	
<i>r</i>	Degree	<i>p</i>	Interpretation
0.01	Slight correlation	0.902	No significance

Table 6 shows the significant relationship between the level of acceptance towards heteronormative beliefs and clinical performance rating of 4th year BSN students ($p=0.902$) where the analysis was at 95% level of confidence. There is no significant relationship between the level of acceptance towards heteronormative beliefs and clinical performance rating of 4th year BSN students as shown by the p-values which are above 0.05 level of significance. The result implied that the level of acceptance to heteronormative beliefs does not affect the clinical performance of 4th year BSN students. Therefore, the researcher “fail to reject” the null hypothesis.

The result of the study is further supported by the study of Habarth (2015) where the acceptance of heteronormative ideas may be linked to unfavorable feelings about gender nonconformity and individuals who are traditionally gender conforming may also be badly affected by heteronormative ideas (Croft et al., 2015).

Though the level of acceptance to heteronormative beliefs does not affect the clinical performance, Stokes (2019), in his study, emphasized that nurses must ensure that they have the clinical competency to care for LGBTQ patients in order to give quality care to all of their patients. Nurses felt more prepared to care for LGBTQ patients in any clinical setting after attending educational seminars, training, and open discussions (Margolies et al., 2014). It was important to note that training and education should be ongoing rather than limited to a single educational event according to Leininger (1988, as cited by Hall, 2021). The phrases and vocabulary used by LGBTQ people were likely to alter and adapt. As a result, nurses must keep up with current terminology (Eliason & Chinn, 2018). Nurses who have received adequate training are more likely to use inclusive language, perform essential exams, and provide a welcoming environment for LGBTQ patients. Nurses can start to change the current trend in LGBTQ patients' health culture by implementing these best practices (Eliason & Chinn, 2018). Nursing students have a unique opportunity to improve the current healthcare culture for LGBTQ patients as they enter the industry (Eliason & Chinn, 2018). Nursing students will be better prepared to care for this patient population and improve patient outcomes by enhancing undergraduate nursing education and training on LGBTQ patient care. These nurses can set an example by receiving additional training in LGBTQ clinical care. Their coworkers will also learn how to speak in an inclusive manner and create a welcoming environment for LGBTQ patients (Eliason & Chinn, 2018).

Conclusions

The following conclusions were reasonably formed based on the presented findings. The researcher came to the conclusion that the high level of heteronormative acceptance among 4th year BSN students could be attributed to negative attitudes about gender conformity and gender non-conformity after conducting a comprehensive study.

Furthermore, the students' clinical performance demonstrated that a very good clinical performance may be achieved regardless of sex, sexual orientation, or religion. This means that any beliefs these students hold will have no bearing on their ability to provide appropriate treatment to their patients. Students should be encouraged and given knowledge about gender development as well as topics connected to LGBTQ communities to further improve the quality of care for patients with diverse cultural norms. Students may be able to provide a safe space not only for heterosexuals, but also for sexual minorities, in this manner.

The sex, sexual orientation, and religion of the students had no bearing on their acceptance to heteronormative beliefs. The acceptability of heteronormative norms and culture has already been shaped by previously established norms in the society.

The clinical performance of nursing students does not depend on the aforementioned variables. As nurses, they are trained to provide quality care to all kinds of patients without bias and prejudice; and that the care they provide are bounded by the Code of Ethics for Nurses. As theorized by Madeleine Leininger, there should be encouragement of culturally congruent care among varied and diverse populations.

The level of acceptance to heteronormative beliefs does not affect the clinical performance of 4th year BSN students. Acceptance of these beliefs may be due to other factors such as gender conformity or nonconformity, but that does not mean that patients will not receive the best possible care. Nursing students' clinical performance may increase further if knowledge is shared with a varied group of people, not only among health care practitioners but also among the general public.

The following recommendations are recommended based on the researcher's conclusions.

The “high” level of acceptance to heteronormative beliefs may have contributed to personal factors in every individual. Students and the instructors must adhere with the Nurses’ Code of Ethics to treat all patients equally regardless of sex, sexual orientation, religion and other factors that encompasses diversity among people.

The “very good” clinical performance among students must be maintained.

Students must be taught on specific issues and concerns about gender inclusion with the support of school administrators and collaboration with both academic and clinical coordinators, and it will address the possibility of discrimination among heterosexuals and sexual minorities. Gender and development programs in schools and healthcare facilities will assist not only the schools, but also the linked institutions and communities through community health teachings during nursing health affiliations. The communities will be educated on a variety of topics, including not only health-related issues, but also gender-sensitive issues that might lead to discrimination, violence, and abuse.

Heteronormative beliefs have been highly accepted in the society. In order to foster inclusivity and equality, clinical educators from various institutions must make it easier to include gender-sensitive practices and mediums of education into the existing nursing curriculum.

The clinical performance of nursing students is not affected by their sex, sexual orientation and religion. To further enhance their clinical competence, clinical instructors should also attend seminars and trainings to improve their gender and development knowledge and skills, as well as sexual minorities and trends in the acceptance to the LGBTQ communities; and that they should be willing to share all of their new ideas and knowledge with their colleagues in order to improve teaching – learning performance while instilling gender-related information among the students and the people of the communities they are affiliated with during RLE exposures.

Nursing students' clinical performance is unaffected by their acceptance of heteronormative beliefs. The existing nursing curriculum must be evaluated and aligned with non-gender-discriminatory roles, expectations, and practices in nursing education, as society may hold differing perspectives on such ideas. Furthermore, nursing manuals and procedures, dress code, and ethical considerations in connection with issues of gender and development must all be thoroughly reviewed to ensure that student nurses are well-informed and that there are no biases or prejudices in nursing practice, regardless of sex, sexual orientation, or religion.

The researcher urges the Commission on Higher Education and the Department of Health to reevaluate existing gender and development programs at colleges and universities, as well as the Department of Health's clinical health institutions, to see if they were implemented properly, appropriately, and effectively. All school administrators must examine and restore gender equality and gender development programs in order to reduce and eliminate the frequency of program violations and abuse.

Student nurses must participate in gender equality programs to enhance their knowledge, skills and attitudes towards quality care among diverse populations. The trends in nursing are constantly changing and nurses must have the adaptability to manage patient care by adapting to societal norms while maintaining the values and continually providing effective and quality care to all patients.

Clinical instructors should provide adequate and sufficient knowledge and skills enhancement among their students by adhering to the existing gender equality programs and must have the appropriate learning contents to prevent discriminatory abuse among students and patients with varied perspectives on sexual diversity, as well as provide practices that are non- gender discriminatory and unbiased.

Future researchers must continue to innovate existing gender equality programs that may contribute to the changes in the trend of nursing care and gender-related interventions. Perspectives among sexual diversity and effects of gender conformity and nonconformity are some of the topics that the future researchers might dig in further to identify factors that may affect heteronormative acceptance and how the field of nursing can contribute to both nurses and patients in diverse populations.

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